

EXCAVATIONS & EXPLORATIONS

Interpreting Transformation of Material Culture with Reference to Stratigraphy: Report on the Excavation at Bowalar Mandap Mound, Birampur, Dinajpur, Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT: In this paper, an initial attempt is made to understand the ‘early medieval’ ways of life and settlements of the people living in the hinterland zone between two contemporary urban centres – Pundranagar (Mahasthangarh) and Kotivarsa (Bangarh) – on the basis of archaeological excavation conducted within the stratigraphic framework offered by the Harris Matrix method. The method enables us to incorporate and engage with the complex factors and processes at work, including the history of the landscape and rivers as the crucial factors in societal transformation along with the other politico-religious and economic factors and processes. Fundamentally, this paper is the report of the excavation on the finds of a Buddhist *Stupa*-shrine in Bowalar Mandap Mound at Dinajpur of Bangladesh, and attempts to use the retrieved data to engage with the understanding and interpreting the culture and settlement in the zone. It has been found that shifts in the rivers and alluvial landscapes played their part in conjunction with the socio-religious and economic factors in the transformation of this particular Buddhist votive *Stupa*-shrine which was later converted into a Brahmanical edifice. My argument is that the transformations, and their conditions and processes, might be proved to be significant in verifying and re-thinking the dominating ‘early medieval’ history of this part of *Varendri* in future studies.

KEYWORDS: Stratigraphy, transformation of material culture, shifts in alluvial landscape, Buddhist *Stupa*-shrine, rethinking ‘early medieval’ history.

CONTEXT: LOCATION, LANDSCAPE, OBJECTIVES AND THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL ‘PLACE’

A convex top structural mound (DNP.BRP.8),¹ locally known as Bowalar Mandap, was selected for excavation. The mound (25°25.264’ N and 89°00.238’ E) is located in Sandalpur Mauza of Khanpur Union of Birampur upazila in Dinajpur district within the land owned by the forestry department. On the basis of spatial patterning of archaeological places recognized and recorded in full-coverage survey in the upazila (Sen 2012), the mound has been categorized as a discrete or isolated archaeological place which was not included within the spatial boundary of any archaeological settlement defined, mostly, on the basis of degree of clustering of archaeological places, including artificial water bodies or tanks. The place, as the analyses of the survey data revealed, nevertheless, is associated culturally, behaviourally, and temporally with the archaeological settlement of Charkai (BRP.CLS.6)² (Pl. 3).

The primary objective of the excavation was to understand and interpret archaeological stratigraphy in the way that is facilitated by the Harris Matrix method (Harris 1989; Spence 1990; Barker 1993; Bernard, et al. 2001). Although this method is not unique and many archaeological sites in the world have been excavated following the single context recording, very few archaeological sites in South Asia, including Bangladesh, have been excavated following this method. Selection of the primary objective was, thus, conditioned by this actuality that made us incorporate this method for an isolated mound in the context of Bangladesh. The complementary aim, besides, was to exploit the potentials offered by this method for detailed understanding of the events – both cultural and natural – through stratigraphy. These objectives were validated on the background of a tradition of excavation that dominated by a monument-centric (or treasure hunting type) distorted version of the method of the Wheeler-Kenyon school. The secondary

FIG. 1. The structural mound before the excavation (view from the east).

objective was to interpret historical processes understood and interpreted from the excavated remains and to relate that history with the accepted socio-cultural history of the area predominantly based on textual and epigraphic sources, if it was possible. Any kind of stratigraphic understanding is absent in the previous excavations in the area (see, Ahmed 1979; personal communication with Musa 1984-85), that was part of the sub-regional unit of Varendri and, probably, Pundra, and that is situated in the hinterland zone in between two prominent urban centres of the region – Mahasthangarh (Pundranagara, the capital of *Pundrabardhana Bhukti* from ‘early historic’ to ‘early medieval’ period) and Bangarh (Kotivarsha, the urban centre that was central to *Kotivarsha Visaya* during the aforesaid period) (Pl. 4).

The mound measured 19 m (east to west) × 22 m (north to south), and is 1.54 m high from the plains to the south and 5 m high from the plain lying on the east. The mound was selected for excavation because of its very specific setting on a juncture of various landscape units (Figs 1 and 2). An abandoned channel of Karatoya river system, locally known as the Asur river, previously known as Asuli river (Buchanon-Hamilton 1833), flows to the north and the north-west of the mound. Relatively elevated landform of the tectonically uplifted terrace—popularly identified as Barind—is to the south. Although the terrace is attributed to mid-late Pleistocene, there

FIG. 2. The structural mound before the excavation from the abandoned bed of Asuli River (view from the north).

are many pockets of Holocene deposits on it. In several areas the terrace is dissected. The mound is located in one of the areas with broad dissection with strongly to moderately developed soils. The dissection has created undulated topography of the terrace. A low-lying seasonally flooded depression, occupying the dissection, lies to the east and the south of the mound. Simultaneously, the mound is on the recent alluvium fill within this low lying dissections and deposition is from the channels of Karatoya River System. Along with the preliminary objectives enumerated above, the additional cause for the selection of this particular archaeological place for excavation was to understand the nature of palaeo surface and soils on which the deposits stand and to find out whether this particular unique location of the mound in a juncture of three types of landform have had any impact on the history of the transformation of the deposits and material culture.

The temporary benchmark (TBM) was extrapolated from the digital elevation model and 33 m from MSL was taken as the datum point for the excavation.

The mound had low gradient slope [$>45^\circ$] on the north, the east and the south. However, the slope on the west was very steep [$>60^\circ$], as it could be understood from the contour map (Fig. 3). The top was flat and with thick vegetation cover. The mound also stands on the western edge of the deciduous forest cover (mainly of *Shorea robusta*).

FIG. 3. Contour map of the structural mound.

A 5 × 5 m trench (T7) was taken on the northern edge of the mound and it was extended to another 5 m to the north as T7.2. Later the trench was extended towards the south, the west and the east, and the open area approach was appropriated for recording.

THE EXCAVATION: STRATIGRAPHY AND TRANSFORMATIONS

Four different periods have been interpreted after the building of the stratigraphic matrix. The contexts (deposits, cuts, and masonries) of these periods, and their interpretive interconnections and temporal sequences are as follows:

FIG. 4. Pavements Pav. 2056 and Pav. 2093 (oblique view from the south).

Level 1: This period of the site is represented by flimsy remains of pavements (?) made of flat bricks exposed in T7.2. Two pavement-like structures, Pavement 2056 and Pavement 2093 (Fig. 4), were found to be sloping towards the abandoned channel to the north. Pavement 2093 (Fig. 5) is made of three courses of bricks and Pavement 2056, made of single course of bricks, lies to the north of the former. The single course pavement measures 1.94 m (north-south) and 1.57 m (east-

FIG. 5. Composite plan of Level 1.

west) and its depth varied from 32.30 to 32.45 m. The brick pavement with three courses is destroyed by the construction activities of the later brick-built structures (Fig. 6). On the other hand, the pavement made of three courses of bricks measures 1.51 m (east-west) and 31 cm (north-south). The southern part of this pavement was cut and filled by the deposits on which the later construction was made (Fig. 7).

The deposits overlying these pavements mostly correspond to the demolition and other slope-wash debris. However, possibly one of the most significant deposits is revealed as just overlying these pavements. 2053 and 2054 correspond to a particular depositional environment. 2054 is soft, medium to coarse brown sand overlain by light greyish finer silty particles. Inclusions include >15% small brick fragments. Being 3-10 cm in thickness, this particular deposit is above another deposit of loose, greyish brown sandy silt (2053) with 10-24 cm in thickness. These particular deposits, extended mainly horizontally over the pavements, represent a possible sedimentary facies of overbank flooding. The soil on which the later building was constructed and the soil on which the pavements were constructed has particular similarity; yet, these deposits with their possible deposition by a low to moderate energy regular flood from the adjacent channel are not detectable vertically.

FIG. 6. The northern wall of the blind cells that were built by cutting the pavements of earlier period (oblique view from the north).

FIG. 7. Pavements overlain by flood-born sandy silt.

The pavements and the later structures are constructed on a sticky, hard, grey silty clay horizon at the depth of 32.26 m and the altitude of the horizon corresponding level of the pavements under the walls of later structures is at 32.50 m. This layer is made of fine, white, massive silty sand with few, fine to medium, moderately sorted, faint, yellowish mottles, and pellets. This layer was possibly deposited after the abandonment of the pavements and associated structures, the nature of which cannot be determined as they might have been destroyed through the construction of the later structures. This layer also represents a low energy flood deposited sedimentary facies (Fig. 8). All these sedimentary evidences along with 2060 under the later structure indicate that more than one flood sequence, probably seasonal in nature, occurred after the destruction and abandonment of the earliest structural remains of the site.

Most importantly the later structures were built on a palaeosol which is a stage 3-4 soils

FIG. 8. The flood-born sandy and silty facies (planimetric view) in Level 1.

of our lithopedostratigraphy.³ They are not older alluvium of the region, rather they represent the recent alluvial sediments with initial sign of soil formation.

Objects from this level include an iron nail (BLM.2043.1) that is possibly a later intrusion (Fig. 9).

Level 2: This level represents the first major detectable and comprehensive construction activity on the site. Three architectural components represent this period. First, three sequential layers

FIG. 9. An iron nail (BLM.2043.1) from Level 1.

of soil, brick soling and indurated floor on the palaeosurface (Fig. 10); secondly, blind cells on the north, the east and the south and, thirdly, brick built structural remains constituting a solid square platform with the base of a circular structure at its centre, and surrounding walls forming a square around the solid structure.

The outer walls (W. 2094 on the south, W. 2096 to the east, W. 2030 to the north) of the blind cells are at the distance of 1.65 m on the south, 1.55 m to the east, and 1.22 m to the north from the enclosure wall. There are two walls joining these walls to the enclosure wall on these above directions, except the north-east corner where the joint wall has not been excavated. These walls are JW. 2095, JW. 2085, JW. 2097, JW. 2117, and JW. 2024.

The depth of the outer wall W. 2030 of the blind cells was measured as excavation was conducted inside the blind cell and outside on the north in T7.2. The height of the wall (W. 2030) is 1.02 m (top 33.52 m, bottom 32.50 m) on the north-east and 1.47 m (top 33.97 m and bottom 32.50 m) on the north-west. On the other hand,

FIG. 10. The indurated floor (Fl.2033) (vertical view).

the joint wall (JW. 2024) measures 40-50 cm in thickness. The outer wall and the joint wall rest on firm, sticky, light grey sandy silt with dark grey mottles, with occasional occurrence of charcoal patches, and Fe-Mn segregates (2049). There are

FIG. 11. Complete brick soling (Flp. 2043) (under the floor 2033).

very few powdered bricks, possibly derived from colluvial wash of the eroded portion of the deposits from earlier level.

A soling made of complete bricks (Flp. 2047) (Figs 11 and 12) was laid upon a 31-36 cm thick deposit of dark grey, clayey silt (2052, from 33.20 to 33.59 m, equivalent to 2040, 2049 to the north) with occasional occurrence of blackish Fe-Mn mottles. Poorly sorted, moderate occurrences of small to medium potsherds were recorded from this particular deposit. The potsherds had black coatings of Fe-Mn segregates, possibly owing to the water-logging by fluctuation of water and overbank flooding of the abandoned channel. Radiocarbon date from a charcoal sample (Laboratory code: Ly-15174) from 2040 (BLM.2007.2040.S2) gives an interesting date of -1800 ± 30 BP with the calibrated age of 131-321 CE (most probable date is 235 CE). At the same time, the light gray deposit of sandy silt (2045), with occasional occurrence of powdered bricks under 2040, revealed charcoal, frequent Fe-Mn segregates supplied another sample (BLM.2007.2045.S1), which was dated (Laboratory code: Ly-15175) to -1810 ± 30 BP, with the calibrated range of 129-314 CE (with maximum probability range of 130-260 CE and most probable date of 228 CE). These two dates are anomalous if we consider the stylistic and formal attributes of the structural remains, and

FIG. 12. Brick soling that acted as floor preparation level, floor (Fl.2033) and the wall constructed over them.

pottery assemblages. Rather, I think the charcoal samples and their spatial context within the sedimentary matrix make them more naturally formed than culturally originated. In this sense, these sedimentary deposits could be dated to not before the early centuries of the first millennium and undoubtedly, their sedimentary location on the bank of a river, texture and their correlation with our regional litho-pedo stratigraphy indicate that they were typical floodplain sediments with incipient soil development.

The soling (Fpl. 2047) (Figs 11 and 12) was made of complete bricks (they measure from $34 \times 23 \times 6$ cm to $36 \times 22 \times 5$ cm). These complete bricks were overlain by an indurated, 10-12 cm, yellowish red floor (Fl. 2033, equivalent to Fl. 2074) made of powdered bricks in clay matrix (Fig. 13).

The enclosure wall and the solid square were built upon this floor. The use of blind cells and deposit of potsherd (2052) to raise ground and

FIG. 13. The floor (Fl.2074) equivalent to Fl.2043 within the rectangular chamber.

consolidate the soil were further modified with the use of complete brick soling and thick indurated floor to raise the space like a terrace for facilitating the construction of the structures above. It could be proposed that this construction method by cellular structure and raised terrace was specifically suitable for building of structures on comparatively soft sediments with incipient soil formation. This method, without doubt, made it possible to bear the load of the structures above. At the same time, protection from regular overbank annual flooding of the adjacent channel was attained. However, the apparent absence of blind cells on the western side is interesting. Although blind cells on the western side were not sought by excavation, the walls from the northern and southern side did not continue towards the west. The slope of the mound on that particular side is steep ($>60^\circ$). It can be checked if there are any blind cells on this side.

As has been explicit from the above discussion, the square solid platform with a circular base at its centre was surrounded by walls on four cardinal directions. Among this the wall to the west was destroyed by the later constructions. The wall to the north (W. 2010), wall to the east (W. 2062) and wall to the south (W. 2063) with the absent wall to the west forms a square area which measures 7.75 m from the north to the south and 8.05 m from the east to the west. The solid square structure (Pl. 2007) is placed almost at the centre of this square. It measures 3.45 m (from the south to the north) and 3.40 m (from the east to the west). The space between the solid square platform and the walls on the north and on the south measures 1.25 m and the wall on the east measures 1.32 m.

The circular structure, 1.12 m in diameter, was cemented to the centre of the solid structure (Pl. 2005) by a deposit of rammed powdered bricks (Fl. 2013). The solid platform was constructed by building a hollow square first and then, by filling the hollow with brick fragments (Fig. 14).

All these walls and structures were cemented to the indurated floor by a 3-5 cm thick layer of dark grey sticky clay (2025). This level could be dated with a sample from a deposit of filling

FIG. 14. Composite plan of Level 2.

(2034). This sample (BLM. 2007.2034.S6) has given a date (Lab. Code. Ly. 15173) of 1325 ± 35 BP. The calibrated date is 649-771 CE with the most probable date 669. The structure was constructed, it could be assumed, sometimes on around seventh-eighth centuries CE.

The architectural organization of the walls and platform of this level suggest that this is the layout of a Buddhist *Stupa*-shrine. The central solid structure with the remains of the circular structure is the main *stupa*. The square is the base/*medhi* of the *stupa* and the circular remain is probably the base of the dome/*anda* of the *stupa*. The space between the *stupa* and the enclosure wall in this level was used as the *pradakkhṣina patha*/ambulatory passage. This particular structure has strong resemblance with a votive *stupa*

revealed in the courtyard of Somapura Mahavihara (Paharpur) (Fig. 15).

Interestingly, no complete bricks were used for the construction of the walls, except the floor-preparation level of Flp. 2047. The walls and solid structure seem to be very fragile and weak. One reason for this particular kind of construction could be the geomorphological location of the monument as it is on the unconsolidated sediments of recent flood deposits. Another reason could be its construction in a hasty manner by reusing construction materials from some earlier structures. Construction style of W. 2003 and W. 2065 (Fig. 16) is also indicative of this particular phenomenon of construction. Was this structure constructed under some kind of financially and politically unsettled state? Was it constructed

FIG. 15. A votive stupa in the courtyard of Somapura Mahavihara.

for speedy makeover of the destruction of earlier structure? Or, is it possible to consider this construction style as reflective of the contemporary state of local governance and economy? It is difficult to assume on the basis of materials found from such a small-scale excavation.

The *Stupa-shrine* is possibly associated with the Charkai settlement which is composed of several structural mounds and habitational deposits exposed on surface and on accidental sections of pits as dumped deposits. The mound of Chor Chakrabarty Dhap (DNP.BRP.5) is supposedly has a buried Buddhist *Vihara*, as it has been in-

FIG. 16. The construction of the wall 2065 that was added later to the south for the construction of the rectangular chamber.

ferred from a test trench on that mound (Zakaria 2011: 99-100). It is also interesting to point at the relative isolation of this *stupa* from its associated and contemporary religious establishments. An unidentified object and an iron slag (BLM. 2034.1) (Fig. 17) have been found from this level.

Level 3A: This period is marked by a decisive shift in the layout of the structures. Enclosure wall on the west was destroyed and three walls were added to the square solid structure. W. 2064 is in the same orientation as the enclosure wall on the west. Two walls in east-west orientation was added to this wall (W. 2003 and W. 2065) and adjoined to the solid platform. Thus a rectangular cell was formed on the west over the ambulatory passage of the earlier level. The cell measures 3.28 m from the north to south, and 1.68 m from the east to west (Fig. 18).

At the same time, two small walls made of three courses of bricks were added to the north-west and south-west of the square solid structure (W. 2026 and W. 2082) (Fig. 19) after raising the level of the rest of the space of the ambulatory passage. Thereby the space is now compartmentalized and divided into four parts. The cell on the west, two compartments on the north and south, and a *veranda* like compartment on the east. No corresponding floor has been detected in the compartments of the north, the south and the east. They seem to be demolished by the later constructions and modifications. However, the

FIG. 17. Iron slag (?)[BLM.2034.1].

FIG. 18. Composite plan of Level 3A.

FIG. 19. A post hole on the small wall (W.2082) added later in the ambulatory passage to the eastern side.

FIG. 20. Iron slags (?) [BLM.2025.1].

floor of the rectangular cell seems to be much lower than the floors in other parts. The floor is same as previous level, Fl. 2074, with the altitude of 34.40-34.59 m. This level suggests that the nature and function of the structure might have changed as the transformation of the entire layout indicates. The object from this level is shown in figure 20. Pottery from level 2 suggest that the date of this level must not be placed before tenth-eleventh centuries CE.

Level 3B: The level also marks a major change in the structural layout (Fig. 21). In the cell to the west, the floor was raised by adding a filling of grey, loose, sandy silt (2046 = 2093), 56-60 cm in thickness. A floor preparation level, Flp. 2036, made of flat-bedded medium to large brick

fragments, was constructed on this filling. An indurated floor level, yellowish red in colour and made of small to very small brick fragments, Fl. 2032 (Fig. 22) was built upon this floor-preparation level. It was 16-26 cm in thickness and covered the rectangular cell.

The small walls of the previous level (W. 2026 and W. 2082) were covered by a floor preparation level made of flat-bedded brick fragments (Flp. 2083 (Fig. 23), Flp. 2016). And a strongly cemented floor, Fl. 2061 (Fig. 24) = Fl. 2080 = Fl. 2084, was constructed on the space between solid square (Plat. 2007) and the walls on the north, the east and the south. A small staircase (Str. 2066) was added to the north-east corner of Plat. 2007.

Fig. 21. Composite plan of Level 3B.

FIG. 22. Another floor (Fl. 2032) as one of the relayed floors within the rectangular chamber.

It is quite clear from this level that the central solid square was used very differently than the level 2, and possibly, than the level 3A. Use of the staircase implies that the users climbed up to the top of this supposed *stupa* at this time and used its upper surface. Does this change in the use of the solid structure? Does the space to the east signify a change in the religious or functional nature of the structure? The change might have taken place with the change in the plan and the abandonment of the ambulatory passage in level 3A and division of the space between the solid structure and the sustained enclosure walls to the

FIG. 23. The floor preparation level (Flp. 2083) within the ambulatory passage under the floor (Fl. 2061 = Fl. 2080 = Fl. 2084).

FIG. 24. Floor in the ambulatory passage (Fl. 2061) with a small step to climb to the base of the *stupa*.

south, the north and the east. The introduction of the rectangular cell to the west could also be concomitant to this change.

As far as the chronology of this particular phase is concerned on the basis of a few potsherds, it is possibly not later than twelfth century CE.

Level 3C: The difference between this level and the previous one is only in the construction of a relayed floor within the rectangular cell (Fig. 25). On a hard, greyish brown, sandy silt filling with >30% very small, poorly sorted brick fragments overlaying Fl. 2032 (Fig. 26), 11-13 cm in thickness, another strongly cemented, reddish yellow floor level (Fl. 2023 = Fl. 2087) (Fig. 27) was constructed. This floor level's altitude varied from 34.61 to 34.75 m.

The other characteristics are same as those of previous level. The date of this phase could be placed on around eleventh-twelfth centuries CE.

FIG. 25. Composite plan of Level 3C.

FIG. 26. The floor preparation level made of bricks on bed under Fl. 2032.

FIG. 27. A rammed floor (Fl. 2023) which represents one of the relayed floors within the rectangular chamber added later to the west.

Level 4: This period marks the latest, yet most fragile construction activities on the relatively abandoned and buried structure (Fig. 28). Although the constructions signify the continuous reuse of the space, yet not all the structures had their same use pattern as the previous levels. All together, this particular level marks the decadence state of the structure and its use.

Patches of activity surface was found to be overlain on the level of Plat. 2007 of earlier period. Most of the portions of the structure were filled up with loose, light grey, silty sand mixed with brickbats. Activity surface or floors were constructed over the filled earth. The detected patches belong to this floor. These patches are Fl. 2002(a)(b)(c), Fl. 2009, Fl. 2057 (Fig. 29), and Fl. 2059 on and around Plat. 2007. These

FIG. 29. Another floor (Fl. 2057) contemporary to Fl. 2009.

FIG. 28. Composite plan of Level 4.

FIG. 30. The storage jar.

patches suggest that the floor was constructed by rammed, small to very small brickbats mixed in clay matrix.

An interesting feature is the location of a storage jar (Fig. 30) on the northern side of the solid structure and its burial under a brick-built drain which makes its outlet by cutting a portion of W. 2010 (Fig. 31 and 32). The location of the storage jar indicates that it might have been used for storing water or to refuse water. After its abandonment, a drain was constructed on it. The location of the drain indicates that it was used to drain out water or other fluids from the platform. It is evident that the storage jar (Jar. 2015) and the drain (Drn. 2011) were associated with activities

FIG. 31. The drain (Drn.2011) above the storage jar.

FIG. 32. The drain and the cut on the northern wall (view from the north).

in which water/fluid was an essential element. It is not simply for the draining out of the rain water, as it was constructed during the latest period only. Usually, water is not an essential element for the religious performances in a Buddhist *stupa*. Rather, in Hindu temples (i.e. in the Siva temple) there is evidence of using storage jar and drain for draining out the water from the sanctum (Sanz 1998).

Why was water or any other fluids used on the platform? Does it indicate any change in the function of the structure? Was this structure transformed into a Hindu edifice? It is difficult to seek for an answer to this particular question, more definitively, with the evidence we have. The absence of any cultural material except pottery is also very crucial to consider. Except the storage jar, no complete pots were found. The potsherds are fragmented and many of them recovered from the deposits under the Fpl. 2049 have been reused as the temper for increasing the compaction of the sediments. No other materials were found in the excavation despite the fact that the monument was not severely robbed after the burial. What can be inferred from this absence?

As far as the pottery assemblage is concerned the date of this level should not be later than fourteenth-fifteenth centuries CE.

The structural assemblages and the layouts are portrayed in figures 33-37.

FIG. 33. The square solid brick built base with the circular *stupa* at the centre.

FIG. 34. The rectangular image chamber that acted as the image shrine to the west of the square solid base of the votive *stupa*.

FIG. 36. The circular *stupa* within the filling of the square solid base; the construction style.

FIG. 35. The enclosure wall to the north of the square solid *stupa* leaning slightly towards the north because of the lateral movement of the consolidating sediments.

FIG. 37. The entire structural assemblage of the votive *stupa*-shrine and the abandoned river bed of Asuli to the north and low land to the north-east (view from the south-west).

Interestingly, the walls of the structure are constructed with small fragments of bricks and they are not solid and massive. One reason for avoiding the heavy construction could be the nature of sediments on which the structure was built. Moreover, the entire structural assemblage did not need to carry a massive superstructure. Presence of postholes (Fig. 38) on the walls suggests that the superstructure could be of wattle-and-daub construction. An iron nail and a fragment of bangle (Fig. 39) were found from this level.

POTTERY ASSEMBLAGE

The pottery from the place is not huge in quantity and their preliminary description along with stratigraphic positions is as follows:

In several instances, potteries were found to be mixed because of the re-use of the structural assemblages. Yet, determination of the temporality of the above levels was attempted with regard to the formal and typological attributes of the potteries that were considered, on the basis of their contextual position, belonging to a particular level.

BLM. 2034.33 (level 2): Fragment of plate of grey ware with outcurved externally thickened rim with corrugated lip. The pot is medium fired, medium fabric (Fig. 40).

BLM. 2034.1 (level 2): Fragment of jug of

FIG. 38. One of the post holes.

FIG. 39. A fragment of glass bangle.

grey ware with externally thickened rim. The pot is medium fired, medium fabric (Fig. 40).

BLM. 2034.28 (level 2): Fragment of cup of red ware with vertical closed rim. The pot is medium fired, medium fabric (Fig. 40).

BLM. 2034.25 (level 2): Fragment of bowl of red ware with flaring undercut rim. Grooved line on the inner surface of the rim portion. The pot is medium fired, medium fabric (Fig. 40).

BLM. 7 (undetermined): Fragment of vase of grey ware with outcurved externally thickened rim with grooved line on the inner surface. Grooved line on the inner surface of the neck. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric.

BLM. 2043.3 (level 1): Fragment of bowl of grey ware with outcurved externally thickened rim with groove. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric (Fig. 41).

BLM. 2034.34 (level 2): Fragment of vase of red ware with splayed out rim with groove on the outer and inner surface. Groove line on the outer and inner surface of neck. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric (Fig. 42).

BLM. 2034.4 (level 2): Fragment of cup of red ware with closed rounded rim. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric (Fig. 42).

BLM. 2052.2 (level 2): Fragment of large bowl of red ware with vertical rim thickened on the top. Concave curve on the neck towards the base. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric with mica (Fig. 42).

FIG. 40. Profile of pottery assemblages found from different levels.

BLM. 2042.4 (level 2): Fragment of storage jar of grey ware with outcurved rim. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric with thin section, suggesting water-logged condition.

BLM. 2034.14 (level 2): Fragment of vase of grey ware with flaring externally thickened rim. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric (Fig. 42).

BLM. 2006.2 (surface): Fragment of storage jar of red ware with externally thickened vertical rim. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric (Fig. 44).

BLM. 2041.2 (level 2): Fragment of unidentified pot of grey ware with externally thickened rim. The pot is well fired with less mica (Fig. 43).

BLM. 2043.9 (level 1): Fragment of large

bowl of red ware with rounded rim. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric (Fig. 41).

BLM. 2098.11 (undetermined): Fragment of jug of red ware with outcurved undercut rim with groove on the top and outer surface. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric.

BLM. 2034.10 (level 2): Fragment of bowl of grey ware with flaring ledged rim with incised design on the inner surface and groove line on the outer surface. The pot is well fired, medium fabric (Fig. 40).

BLM. 2098.2 (undetermined): Fragment of bowl of red ware with flaring rim. Corrugated line on the inner and outer surface of the pot. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric.

BLM. 2042.2 (level 2): Fragment of large bowl

FIG. 41. Profile of pottery assemblages found from different levels.

of grey ware with outcurved rim with groove on the inner surface. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric, indicating water-logged condition with Fe-Mn segregations on the surface (Fig. 43).

BLM. 2091.3 (level 3B): Fragment of small bowl of red ware with internally thickened rim with corrugated line under the rim. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric (Fig. 44).

BLM. 2034.7 (level 2): Fragment of vase of red ware with splayed out rim. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric with red slip.

BLM. 2043.1 (level 1): Fragment of storage jar of red ware with externally thickened rim with groove and wavy line on the outer surface. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric (Fig. 41).

BLM. 2037.1 (level 2): Fragment of storage jar of red ware with splayed out undercut rim. The pot is moderately fired, medium fabric.

FIG. 42. Profile of pottery assemblages found from different levels.

FIG. 43. Profile of pottery assemblages found from different levels.

FIG. 44. Profile of pottery assemblages found from different levels.

It must be noted that the above description is provisional and the categorization of pottery assemblage according to stratigraphy is currently undergoing.

CONCLUSIONS: INTERPRETATIVE PROPOSITIONS AND INFERENCES

In the previous sections of this paper, a number of questions have been raised with regard to the evidence found and inferred from the excavation. Considering the spatial and temporal extent of Varendri, findings from a small isolated structural mound as such cannot be regarded as a basis for wide generalizations about the life ways of the past people and history of social dynamics of Varendri. The accepted wisdom on the history of the region and area dominated by interpretations of textual and epigraphic sources, nevertheless, could be problematized with the stratigraphic evidences of structural transformations and associated sedimentological evidences. Re-use of structural edifice in different periods is not uncommon in the sub-continent. The pattern and sequences of re-use with a detailed stratigraphy, however, have rarely been attended to in archaeological discourses.

The place and the structure that was primarily constructed and functioned as a Buddhist votive *Stupa*-shrine were under continuous use, approximately from the seventh to fifteenth centuries CE. The flimsy remains of level 1, it seems, might not be earlier than the seventh century CE, as far as the pottery assemblage denotes. The structural assemblage and its layout did not change its organization in a straightforward way. Rather, it is quite likely that the transformation of the layout suggests the functional changes of the edifice. From a Buddhist *stupa*, probably votive, in nature, it was transformed into a Buddhist *Stupa*-shrine with the added chamber to the west serving possibly as the *garbhagr̥ha* (*sanctum*). Again, the structure was later converted, with all the probability, into a Brahmanical edifice.

Axiomatically, it is accepted in a homogenizing way in the established historical narratives that the decline of Buddhism and growth and

dominance of Brahmanism in Varendri, (and in Bengal) is coincidental to the rise of Sena dynasty in the twelfth century CE. On the contrary, and simultaneously, through the interpretations of epigraphic sources, it has also been assumed that in spite of gradual merging of common Buddhist mass into Brahmanical society during post-eighth-century period during the development of *Tantric* Buddhism in this part of Indian subcontinent, there was an atmosphere of tolerance in the life of the ordinary. As a support, various instances of persons of Brahmanical faith patronizing Buddhist establishments have also been referred to on the basis of the interpretations of epigraphic data (Sircar 1975: 183-205 for example). This historical narrative takes textual and epigraphic sources for granted. The dominating scholarly practice is inclined, moreover, towards the use of archaeological data (often, very unsystematically and sporadically gathered from a wide spatial scale) in support of the biased interpretations of textual and epigraphic sources. Archaeological data, especially collected from systematic stratigraphic context are not seriously endorsed by the scholars to verify the explanations of epigraphic and textual records. I do not simply argue for a 'superiority' of archaeological data in 'history writing' as more 'factual' and 'objective'. That would be a vulgar modernist call (Lucas 2001, 2004). What I want to call for is to incorporate archaeological data, defined in terms of stratigraphic understanding of excavations, for verification of accepted wisdom.

What does the stratigraphy of Bowalar Mandap hint at in spite of its limitation as a spatially isolated archaeological place and in spite of the limitation of treating the place as a valid sample of past Varendri region?

It must be asserted that this place must be addressed and understood not in isolation. The archaeology of this place is enmeshed into the associated settlement of Charkai where a Buddhist *vihara* was detected through exploratory excavation. The settlement structure was defined primarily by the location of this *vihara* and this particular spatial matrix suggests overtly that in this case and in several other cases in the study area,

Buddhist *vihara* was not isolated from the contemporary rural settlements. Rather, my findings indicate that Buddhist and Brahmanical establishments were situated at the core of the formation and development of rural settlements in ‘early medieval’ Varendri. These archaeological evidences negate the canonical interpretation about the Buddhist *samgha* and Buddhist *vihara* that they were situated away from the settlements to get along with their austere ways of renunciation and meditative practices. The accepted knowledge on history of Buddhist *samgha* and Buddhist establishments in Varendri, as far as the results of full-coverage survey and excavations hint, must be rethought. The complicated details of these new alternatives are not presented in this paper, as it would require different space and treatment. I will attempt to perform that task later in some other essay. The point which is essential to emphasize is that the particular settlement structure suggests that the settlement patterning in ‘early medieval’ Varendri constituted the activity area with probable habitational zone created and sustained by taking the religious establishments at their core. Buddhist establishments did not necessarily inhabit an isolated peripheral existence; rather they acted and were acted upon as the core of early medieval rural settlements in this part of Varendri.

It has been pointed at that the increase of Brahmanical settlements is evident from post-tenth centuries onwards from epigraphic evidences, especially the land grants⁴ (Furui 2007; Sen 2012). Brahmanical control and intervention, testified from the epigraphic sources, are not universally supported by data from archaeological survey and excavations, at least in this part of Varendri. The transformation of the layout of the structure in level 3A, 3B and in level 4 of Bowalar Mandap respectively during tenth-eleventh centuries CE and thirteenth-fourteenth centuries CE could be interpreted as some kind of functional change of the structural assemblages. Between these two stages transformations in level 3B and 4 could be identified with more probability as a Brahmanical shift. But the chronology of this particular level is much later than the period

when the Brahmanical expansion and infiltration had begun according to the epigraphic records.

Interestingly, these changes might not always be hypothesized as an outcome or an effect of the expansion of Brahmanism. It must be noted that only a very few archaeological places have been excavated in comparison to the number of places that have been recorded through the survey in only seven *upazila/thanas* in Dinajpur and Joypurhat districts of north-western part of Bangladesh. It has been pointed earlier that the settlement of Charkai, which is spatially associated with this excavated place has a structural mound called Chor Chakrabartyr Dhap. Exploratory excavations on the site in 1972-73 suggest that there is a Buddhist *vihara* buried under this mound (Zakaria 2011: 99-100). It must be clarified that I am not arguing here to deny the growing influence of Brahmanism. Yet the influence seems to be spatially varied in Varendri with differential conditions, articulations and outcomes, as far as careful recording and interpretation of fresh archaeological data convey. Interpretation of stratigraphy from the excavation of other structural sites (Sen 2012), supports a particular pattern of reuse of the edifices, at least, till fifteenth century CE.

At the same time, the temporality of level 4, moreover, contests the taken-for-granted notion that with the conquest by Ikhtyar al-Din Muhammad Bin Bakhtyar Khalji on around 1204/1205 CE, Islam expanded throughout Bengal. On the contrary, level 4 might be concurrent to the period of the initiation of the rise of Islam in this part of Bengal. This level suggests, at least on this archaeological place, that transformation processes of a Buddhist edifice into a Brahmanical one could be concomitant with the initial phase of other transformations brought about by the beginning of the expansion of Islamic religious dynamics in the social history of this zone of north-western part of present Bangladesh. The transformations denote that boundary of the religious communities was fuzzy and, contestations and conflicts existed within complex articulations of power among different actors and communities. These are the evidences that

indirectly hint towards a cultural milieu that was not merely articulated by a modern desire of the liberal view of tolerance, as we often project it onto pre-colonial past.

This particular instance could become more significant when the route of the expedition to Tibet by Bakhtyar Khalji, as it has been proposed by Zakaria (1979), is taken into account. In contrast to Bhattashali and Major Raverty's proposition, Zakaria contended that Bakhtyar followed a route crossing the area in which the settlement and the place are situated. If the route and the spatial centrality of Bangarh (or Devkot, earlier known as Kotivarsa) – closer in proximity to the settlement and the place – in Bakhtyar's activities are considered, then the evidences of transformation might signify that Brahmanism still had prominence during and after the period of Bakhtyar Khalji's activities in this area. Contrary to the dominant view, dynastic changes, like most of the time, do not essentially concur with religious and cultural changes, and are not necessarily reflected in material culture.

Additionally, according to the analyses of settlement pattern and structure (Sen 2012) on the basis of the data obtained from the full-coverage survey, this particular archaeological place and the associated settlement of Charkai are within a specific zone of settlements or conglomeration of settlements on the right bank of Asuli-Nalshisha-Karatoya rivers. The higher density of settlements and location of this particular zone suggest that these settlements and related isolated places might have had a nodal function in regional settlement pattern and settlement network. I am not presenting the detailed analyses and interpretation of the settlement structure and pattern here. I would like to point out at this particular spatial attribute and the significance of this place as a part of the nodal zone in the regional settlement network.

Sedimentological implications of this excavation could be interesting in a different way. Landscape history is rarely treated seriously to understand social history in accepted disciplinary practice and wisdom. It signifies that a structure was built on alluvium within a presum-

ably changing alluvial landscape in which rivers and their constant shifting bore upon crucial impacts. Interaction between the alluvial landscape and the structure is recognizable in the sediments bearing the signs of regular flooding and water logged conditions owing to the rise of ground water level. The location of the structure on the right bank of the Asuli River is prone to regular flooding of the river. In spite of the fact that regular flooding might not have inundated the structure, the landscape suggests that during the pick monsoon the structure was surrounded on three sides with water that was retained in the low lying lands.

Level 1 suggests that overbank flooding of the channel, being a part of Asuli-Nalshisha-Karatoya river system, to the north had considerable effects on the activities on the place. The construction style of the structure itself indicates that along with the landscape settings, channel processes including regular flooding had to be considered for the construction. As part of the Asuli-Nalshisha-Karatoya river system, the abandonment of the settlement could partially be conditioned by the avulsion of the channel and consequent drying up of the river that was critical for the location and construction of this particular establishment (Sen 2012).

The absence of heterogeneous cultural materials from the excavation needed to be addressed with equal importance. Even the pottery assemblages are homogenous and few in number. The changing function of the place could be a reliable reason for this particular trend. Absence of cultural materials was featured in the sites excavated earlier. In Sitakot *Vihara* and Arun Dhap (where another Buddhist *Vihara* was revealed) (Ahmed 1979; personal communication with Musa 1984-85), similar trend of the paucity of cultural materials was noticed. The relative absence of heterogeneity of material culture is recognizable in other places that were excavated by the author following the same method (Sen 2012). Ahmed (1979) thinks that this particular trend denotes that the 'sites' were not abandoned abruptly; a gradual process of abandonment was inferred, on the contrary. It is very difficult to support this

explanation if the formation processes of archaeological records are taken into account. The paucity of 'cultural materials' cannot simply be explained in terms of gradual abandonment. On the contrary, the stratigraphy of the place and its interpretation might give valuable insights into the phase and processes of abandonment. Multiple factors are required to be considered to understand the processes and factors for abandonment. Along with the socio-religious historical factors, the landscape history must be seriously addressed. The continuous reuse of the place and the edifice tentatively for more than six centuries, besides, must have played a key role for the absence of cultural materials, if there were any. The earlier materials were used for the later deposits and masonries of construction and occupations

The changes in the alluvial geomorphology and the shifts in the hydrological regimes of the river system might have coincided. The Nalshisha-Asuli Rivers and the palaeo-channel remnants along with their courses associated with the place and the settlement of Charkai needs to be considered. One interesting point might be worth mentioning here. In the recent excavations in the *mazar* area by Bangladesh-France Joint Excavation Team, the evidence of an earthquake was detected (Berliet, et al. 2012). The authors have pointed that most of the constructions revealed on site, more precisely those concentrated towards the south, including the biggest living space have been heavily affected by earthquake. The first architectural and technical studies of the earthquake are going on at present (Berliet, et al. [in press], cited in Berliet, et al. 2012). Most of the walls of the living quarters are collapsed from the same direction. The others show undulations, deformations, fractures. All these elements state the importance of the earthquake. The date of this event is difficult to identify.

However, with the aid of textual sources, the earthquake has been identified as occurred during the thirteenth century, after the conquest of Nadia by Ikhtyar al-Din Bakhtyar Khalji. In another article, Berliet, et al. (in press), have suggested that the earthquake occurred in 1255 CE,

the epicentre of which was in Katmandu as the most probable one (cited in Berliet, et al. 2012: 63; note 4). The effect of the earthquake was grand in scale. With the epicentre in Katmandu, the effect would have been more in the study area lying in between the epicentre and Mahasthangarh. The earthquake might have made impact on the regional river system, as another earthquake in 1882 did on Brahmaputra-Karatoya-Teesta system in this part of Bangladesh.

The hypothesis could be surmised in the following way. The earth quake along with neotectonic upliftment of the terrace area and concomitant subsidence of the floodplains, filling the valleys in the terrace, initiated a phase of shifting of the rivers of Asuli-Nalshisha-Karatoya system towards the east on around thirteenth-fourteenth century CE. The flow in Asuli River, that was a perennial and competent channel during the occupational period of the settlement and the mound, shifted to the channels that were antecedent to the present course of Karatoya. Although the impact of earthquake was instigated by a sudden event, the shifts in channel flows and hydrological regime as a whole, was more gradual as a process. The hypothesis is supported by the short term and long term processes involved with the channel evolution and lateral migration of the channels on a regional scale. The processual impacts of channel migration and consequent floods are more evident in the archaeological and geological stratigraphy of the excavated archaeological places lying more downstream of the Nalshisha River. They are also suggested by the features of the floodplain geomorphological features associated with alluvial landscape context of the excavated archaeological places and settlements (Sen 2012).

Whatever interpretations have been attempted above must be dealt with extreme caution, as the evidential basis of the arguments presented in this paper is provisional and still, tentative. However, consideration of the regional scale-survey data along with more stratigraphically contextualized understanding of material culture might give solid foundations to these arguments and supply interpretive proofs for the verification

of the hypotheses. At the same time, it must be remembered that, raising serious and unwanted questions about the accepted history is often nec-

essary for delving into a more nuanced past with the aid of systematically and programmatically gathered archaeological data.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS: This excavation report is a part of my doctoral dissertation. I am indebted to my supervisor Prof. Syed Mohammad Kamrul Ahsan for his patient and affectionate engagements with my works and various emotions for a long time. He also played a key role for arranging the necessary funding for the excavations. My gratitude is immense to my co-supervisor Prof. Jean-François Salles for his support for me and for taking measures to enable the collected samples to be dated in the radiocarbon laboratory in France. The excavation could not have been possible without the support of my students. They are Sajjad Hossein, Sajedur Rahman, Mohammad Kamal Hossen Akanda, Ahmed Sharif Sunny, Musfiqur Rahman Foysal, Ashiqur Rahman, Pantha, Syfur Rahman Polin, Afroza Khan Mita, Urmila Hasnat, Abir Bin Keysar, and many others. I express my thanks to Department of Archaeology, Ministry of Cultural Affairs, Government of the Peoples' Republic of Bangladesh for granting me permission for excavation. The local administration, including the Chairman of Khanpur Union Parishad and Upazila Nirbahi Officer of Birampur Upazila, helped us a lot. The excavated place is within the jurisdiction of the forestry department. They deserve special thanks as they permitted me to excavate. I am also thankful to Prof. S. N. Rajaguru, Prof. Dipak Ranjan Das, Prof. Mozammel Hoque, Dr Ryosuke Furui and Prof. Arun Nag along with others as they provided valuable advice and suggestions regarding the interpretations. Finally, I thank all the people from Dinajpur who have provided great help in different aspects of our work for a long time.

NOTES

1. The number is the unique code number for each archaeological place developed through our full coverage survey in the region. The numbering system was used in my doctoral work (Sen 2012).

2. On the basis of data gathered during fieldwork about the spatial patterning of the archaeological places and tanks, and subsequent analyses of the data in GISci (Geographic Information Sciences) environment archaeological places were categorized into clusters and discrete places. Degree of clustering was the fundamental attribute in this analysis. Each spatially cluster represents, I assumed on the basis of the interpretation of spatial aggregates, behaviourally a settlement of early medieval period.

3. In the geoarchaeological investigations in the study area, continued concurrently with the surveying and excavations, a regional lithopedostratigraphy was constructed. The detailed characteristics of the soils

of each stage are not required to be elaborated upon here. However, briefly it must be noted that the stage 3 soils represent the Holocene alluvium, with no or little development of pedality and with little mottling or oxidization.

4. For example, see Silimpur inscription and Belwa copperplate inscription. The expansion of Brahmanical settlements in eleventh-century *Varendri* by migrations has been pointed at by Furui (2007: 213-15). He mentioned the contents of Silimpur inscription in regard to the emergence of Brahmanical centres in *Varendri* during this particular period. The centre of Sravasti, identified as located somewhere in present Hili-Balurghat region of Dinajpur, has been referred to as one of these centres in *Varendri* (Furui 2007: 213-15; see also Sircar 1990: 294-8). See also Belwa copperplate inscription (Sircar 1951).

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Location of the excavated mound (DNP.BRP.8) and its spatial patterning with regard to archaeological settlements and landscape context

0 0.5 1 2 Kilometers

Legends

International Boundary	Old Tanks
Archaeological Settlements and Isolated Places	NDTMWS
Low land/ Beel /Oxbow Lake	Floodplain
River	HTMSS
Palaeo and Abandoned Channels with Channel Remnants	GRTWMS
Byde /Low Land	BDTMSS
	GRTMSS

↑
N

Location of The Study Area as Hinterland Zone in relation to Mahasthangarh and Bangarh

Legends

- International Boundary
- Rivers
- Thanas of the Study Area

0 5 10 20 Kilometers

PLATE 4